

APPLIED TO THE CURRENT TRAINING PROCESS REQUIREMENTS

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Annotation

The article highlights the advantages of using the main principles and rules of requirements for the current teaching process in the educational process of general education schools.

Key words: Lesson, education, presentation, multimedia, video.

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V state vydeleny preimushchestva ospolzovaniya osponnykh principov i pravil rebovanii k deystvuyushchemu chebnomu procesu v obrazovatelnom protesse obshcheobrazovatelnoy school.

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Abstract

The article highlights the advantages of using the main principles and rules of requirements for the current teaching process in the educational process of general education schools.

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Introduction

In our independent Uzbekistan, the reform of the continuous education system, the reorganization of the education and training process based on new educational standards, special attention is paid to the activity of the teacher and his pedagogical skills.

Perfect organization of the lesson in continuous education is the primary task of the teacher. Lessons conducted at a high level remain in the minds of students for a long time, and have an effective impact on the formation of their faith, beliefs and ideologies. For this reason, the teacher's scientific level, attitude to his duty, enthusiasm for coaching young people, and pedagogical skills are known at the beginning of the lesson. The quality of the lesson also determines the grade of the science teacher.

Main Part

Currently, special attention is paid to the activity of the teacher and his pedagogical skills. Recommendations regarding the use of pedagogical technology in the course of the lesson, which have begun to take place in the pedagogical thinking of teachers working in the educational process, are very

necessary for teachers. Interactive teaching methods aimed at sensing, feeling, controlling oneself, expressing one's thoughts clearly, succinctly and carefully, and using them, are developing with fast pictures and giving positive results. The interactive methods used in teaching created an atmosphere of competition among students, encouraged them to be active, and as a result, students began to learn cooperation.

Any interactive method, when used correctly and purposefully, will teach students to think independently. New pedagogical technology is a process that produces rational ways of the educational system, in which the teacher is the main responsible person. Because its main task is to deliver information to students quickly, accurately and clearly, should be taught to draw conclusions. In this, the student is the main driving force, can read, read, draw, understand the formulas of projections and use tools, have friendly relations with each other, and help each other in solving the problems set before them. their main task is to help.

In mastering the art of teaching, the lesson organized by the teacher, along with being a means of imparting deep knowledge, is the development of independent Uzbekistan, confidence in the future, what the intelligence and work of our people are capable of, a worthy citizen of the society and serves as a mirror of what it takes to become a teacher. The lesson places a great responsibility on the teacher. Currently, the concept of a modern lesson is often mentioned in pedagogy.

It can be seen from the above that the lesson is the main organizational form of education, and it is a didactic activity organized in a strict order with a certain number of regular students and directed towards a specific goal.

What needs to be done to enrich it with new elements that will increase students' interest in the lesson and the requirements of the current teaching process? The modern education system requires not only mastering the knowledge that humanity has discovered, but also familiarization with the issues that society must solve and the students of today must participate in it. Such issues may include the exploitation of space, the peaceful use of atomic energy, the conversion of deserts into fertile lands and gardens, the intensification of agriculture, and so on.

Great changes are taking place in all fields of economy and science, and every teacher should widely acquaint his students with the next reconstructions and achievements in the field of science he teaches. It should be done in a way that is suitable for students and in accordance with the curriculum. The second feature of this requirement is that the pedagogue always cares about expanding the students' range of thought. Thus, teaching methods are activities aimed at fulfilling the educational

tasks of pedagogues and students of theoretical and practical cognitive activities. The following specific requirements are imposed on it:

1. The method of studying the educational material recommended by the teacher should lead to the formation of students' dialectical views, positive characteristics and behavior. From the point of view of this requirement, the method should be educational.
2. The scientific basis of the teaching method should be clear and precise. Only then the teacher can see what problems can be raised and solved by this method, and what problems cannot be solved.
3. The systematicity of training determines its effectiveness.
4. Comprehensibility of the teaching method: the teaching method must be accepted and used by the student, and the method of studying the educational material must be in accordance with the possibilities of acquiring knowledge.
5. The need for awareness and activity of teaching is a very serious requirement.
6. Thoroughness and validity of knowledge is also crucial.
7. It is not possible to pass a lesson without achieving the compatibility of theoretical and practical events in the teaching method.

Changes and updates taking place in the education system, along with giving new knowledge, skills and qualifications to students, inculcate the patriotic ideas of change in relation to society, the state, and nature in our young people. he also intends to instill it in his heart. A set of interrelated requirements represents a generalized model of a pedagogue and, based on it, the following basic requirements: the ability to teach, the ability to educate. Personal qualities that provide the human factor in the educational process are the ability to objectively assess and control the knowledge of learners. Therefore, a teacher pedagogue should have the following qualities in order to fulfill the complex, responsible and urgent tasks set before him and to form new views on the educational process:

- able to deeply understand the essence of modern, scientific and cultural development;
- update the system of knowledge about the world and man from a deep and wide perspective;
- application of educational information technologies and teaching tools in education;
- to have an understanding of the Internet network and be able to use it to increase their knowledge;
- to know the ways of analyzing the effectiveness of pedagogical work and to be

able to evaluate it;

- to develop ideas about family education and upbringing problems;
- to understand the essence of universal and national culture and economic reforms;
- to know how to effectively use pedagogical technologies in the course of the lesson;
- create conditions for students to think and exchange ideas with each other and create a friendly environment;
- knowing how to use technical tools and educational tools, such as educating children through their own research, creativity, initiative, and hard work in order to make them become well-rounded people.

Any method is intended to achieve a goal, and therefore it requires setting a goal, a method of activity to achieve it, and knowing the tools that will help in the implementation of this activity. Any activity requires knowledge of its object. Finally, the method must lead to the goal, otherwise it must be recognized as unfit for its intended purpose.

Teaching methods can be divided into:

- methods that create content and activate special operations of thinking, memory, attention and imagination;
- methods that create problematic and searching situations in the activity of thoughts;
- methods that activate students' experiences and emotions related to mastering the learning material;
- methods of control and self-control of students;
- methods of managing students' spiritual and personal interactions during the teaching process.

Conclusion

Thus, any method requires the purpose of its application, the activities for the implementation of this goal, and the means of performance of the activity. These tools can be objective or intellectual knowledge about the object of activity, necessarily achieving the set goal. All of these are desirable for any method, but not sufficient for teaching methods.

List of used literature: (references):

1. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). Zamonaviy ta'limda axborot texnologiyalari va ularni qo'llash usul va vositalari. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 481-486.
2. Муродов, О. Т. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ КОМНАТ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(26), 91-95.

3. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(32), 194-201.
4. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA FANINI O 'QITISHDA YANGI INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 130-139.
5. MURODOV, O. T. (2023). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
6. Turakulovich, M. O. (2023). DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION OF AN AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEM IN ROOMS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
7. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Turdiboyev, X. (2023). FIZIKA FANINI O 'RGANISHNING YUQORI DARAJADAGI STRATEGIYALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 152-156.
8. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Turdiboyev, X. (2023). TA'LIM SOHASIDA FIZIKANING SAN'AT BILAN ALOQALARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 144-147.
9. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). FIZIKA FANINING BO 'LIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHDAGIDAGI ASOSIY AHAMIYATI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 162-167.
10. Jurakulov, S. (2023). ON THE RELATION OF METAPHYSICS TO PHYSICS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 9-20.
11. Jurakulov, S. (2023). ON THE RELATION OF METAPHYSICS TO PHYSICS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 9-20.
12. Jurakulov, S. (2023). IMPACT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY ON PEOPLE AND THE ENVIRONMENT. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 143-150.
13. Jurakulov, S. (2023). CHANGES IN LANGUAGE DUE TO NEW PHYSICS. Models and methods in modern science, 2(13), 77-87.
14. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). CAPUTA MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI HOSILALAR VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 360-365.
15. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). MAXSUS SOHALARDA KARLEMAN MATRITSASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 137-141.
16. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). APPROXIMATION OF FUNCTIONS WITH COEFFICIENTS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 135-138.

17. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). Applications of the double integral to mechanical problems. *International journal of sciearchers*, 2(2), 101-103.
18. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). FINDING THE MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM VALUE OF A FUNCTION ON A SEGMENT. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 245-248.
19. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). FUNKSIYALARNI KOEFFITSIENTLAR ORQALI FUNKSIYALARNI YAKINLASHTIRISH HAQIDA MA'LUMOTLAR. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 102-110.
20. Sharipova, M. (2023, December). RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN STRAIGHT LINES AND PLANES IN SPACE. In *Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 60-66)*.
21. Sharipova, M. (2023). FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(27), 106-113.
22. Sharipova, M. (2023). CORRECT PLACED AND CORRECT NOT PLACED ISSUES. *Models and methods in modern science*, 2(13), 115-121.
23. Sharipova, M. (2023). HEAT SPREAD EQUATION. *Инновационные исследования в науке*, 2(12), 50-56.
24. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). HIGH MATH SCORE AND INTERVAL ASSESSMENT. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 420-424.
25. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). IN HIGHER MATHEMATICS, THE EXTREMUM OF A MULTIVARIABLE FUNCTION. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 425-429.
26. Sharipova, M. P. (2024). ISSIQLIK TARQALISH TENGLAMASI UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 2(1), 525-532.
27. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). Working with folders in the JAVA programming language. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(5), 232-236.
28. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). INTRODUCING" PROGRAM CONTROL OPERATORS" IN THE JAVA PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(5), 222-231.
29. Sharopova, M. (2023). ARRAY AND ARRAYS INSTALLATION. *Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences*, 2(12), 102-107.
30. Sharopova, M. (2023). JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE HERITAGE TO DO SYNTAX. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 2(12), 82-87.

31. Sharopova, M. (2023). CHOOSE: COMPOSITION OR INHERITANCE. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 96-102.
32. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). JAVA TILI YORDAMIDA OB'EKTGA YUNALTIRILGAN DASTURLASH ASOSLARI BILAN TANISHISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 111-119.
33. Muxayyo Muxtor qizi Sharopova. (2023). INTRODUCING "PROGRAM CONTROL OPERATORS" IN THE JAVA PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 222-231.
34. Muxayyo Muxtor qizi Sharopova. (2023). Working with folders in the JAVA programming language. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 232-236.
35. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. li.(2023). Mobil ilovalar yaratish va ularni bajarish jarayoni. International journal of scientific researchers, 2(2).
36. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. (2023). USE OF ARTIFICIAL NERVOUS SYSTEMS IN MODELING. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 269-273.
37. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11).
38. Quvvatov, B. U. o'g'li . (2023). ALEXNET - TASVIRLARNI TASNIFLASH UCHUN KONVOLYUTSION NEYRON TARMOQ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 77-90.
39. Boboqulova, M. X. (2023). STOMATOLOGIK MATERIALLARNING FIZIK-MEXANIK XOSSALARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 223-228.
40. Xamroyevna, B. M. (2023). ORGANIZM TO 'QIMALARINING ZICHLIGINI ANIQLASH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 50-58.
41. Khamroyevna, M. B. (2023). PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF BIOLOGICAL MEMBRANES, BIOPHYSICAL MECHANISMS OF MOVEMENT OF SUBSTANCES IN THE MEMBRANE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 217-221.
42. Bobokulova, M. K. (2023). IMPORTANCE OF FIBER OPTIC DEVICES IN MEDICINE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 212-216.
43. Mukhtaram Bobokulova Khamroyevna. (2023). Radiation Protection. Dosimetry . Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 4(6), 134-139.
44. Bobokulova, M. K. (2024). TOLALI OPTIKA ASBOBLARINING TIBBIYOTDAGI AHAMIYATI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 517-524.

45. Axmedova, Z. I. (2023). LMS TIZIMIDA INTERAKTIV ELEMENTLARNI YARATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 368-372.
46. Axmedova, Z. (2023). MOODLE TIZIMI VA UNING IMKONIYATLARI. Development and innovations in science, 2(11), 29-35.
47. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). USING THE USEFUL ASPECTS OF THE MOODLE SYSTEM AND ITS POSSIBILITIES. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 201-205.
48. Zulxumor, A. (2022). IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERACTIVE COURSES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. ILMIY TADQIQOT VA INNOVATSIYA, 1(6), 128-132.
49. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) STATISTICAL PACKAGES OF CAPABILITIES. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(12), 781-787.
50. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) CAPABILITIES OF THE STATISTICAL DATABASE LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 274-280.
51. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). CREATION AND PLACEMENT OF INTERACTIVE ELEMENTS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(13), 120-128.
52. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS, ELECTRONIC EDUCATION: TASKS AND OPPORTUNITIES. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 171-177.
53. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). DISADVANTAGES OF ELECTRONIC LEARNING. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 99-109.
54. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). SQL SPECIFICATIONS FOR DATA ANALYSIS. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 113-120.
55. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). Programming Environments for Creating Mobile Applications on the Android Operating System. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 305-309.
56. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). CAPUTO MA'NOSIDAGI KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TO'G'RI MASALALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 375-382.
57. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). BETA FUNKSIYA XOSSALARI VA BU FUNKSIYA YORDAMIDA TURLI MASALALARNI YECHISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 66-76.
58. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). KASR TARTIBLI ODDIY DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 383-390.

59. Latipova, S. S. qizi . (2024). GAMMA FUNKSIYA. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 391-399.
60. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
61. Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal, 1(10), 13-23.
62. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
63. daughter Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. World of Scientific news in Science, 1(2), 163-176.
64. Shahnoza, L. (2023, March). KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA VA BOSHLANG'ICH FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TESKARI MASALALAR. In " Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 8-10).
65. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). RIMAN-LUIVILL KASR TARTIBLI INTEGRALI VA HOSILASIGA OID AYRIM MASALALARNING ISHLANISHI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(12), 216-220.
66. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). MITTAG-LIFFLER FUNKSIYASI VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 238-244.
67. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). KASR TARTIBLI HOSILA TUSHUNCHASI. SCHOLAR, 1(31), 263-269.
68. Tursunov, B. J., & Allanazarov, G. O. (2019). Perspektivnye tehnologii proizvodstva po uluchsheniyu kachestva benzina. Theory and practice of contemporary science, 3(45), 305-308.
69. Турсунов, Б. Ж., & Алланазаров, Г. О. (2019). Перспективные технологии производства по улучшению качества бензина. Теория и практика современной науки, (3 (45)), 305-308.
70. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Analysis of Concepts About the Effect of an Explosion in Solid Wednesday. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 296-304.
71. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Methods of Control of Explosion Energy Distribution in Rocks. Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599), 1(10), 108-117.

72. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). WASTE-FREE TECHNOLOGY FOR ENRICHMENT OF PURIFIC COPPER-ZINC ORE. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 288-293.
73. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). ANALYSIS OF MODERN METHODS FOR OIL SLUDGE PROCESSING. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 280-287.
74. Jumaev, K., & Tursunov, B. (2022, December). Environmentally friendly technology for obtaining fuel briquettes from oil waste. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1112, No. 1, p. 012005). IOP Publishing.
75. Ахмедова, О. Б., Турсунов, Б. Ж., & угли Худойбердиев, Н. Н. (2022). Анализ физико-химических свойств нефтешламов Бухарского НПЗ и рациональные способы их утилизации. Science and Education, 3(6), 495-507.
76. Турсунов, Б. Д. (2016). Анализ и выявление путей совершенствования процессов горного дела. Молодой ученый, (23), 105-106.
77. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). THE MAIN SIGNIFICANCE OF THE DEPARTMENTS OF PHYSICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 162-167.
78. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Turdiboyev, H. (2023). RELATIONSHIPS OF PHYSICS WITH ART IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 144-147.
79. Jurakulov, S. Z. O., & Turdiboyev, H. (2023). ADVANCED STRATEGIES FOR LEARNING PHYSICS. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 152-156.
80. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). IN THE EDUCATIONAL FIELD OF PHYSICS LEVEL AND POSITION. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 157-161.
81. Jurakulov, S. (2023). PROPERTIES AND CHARACTERISTICS OF NUCLEAR ENERGY. Инновационные исследования в науке, 2(12), 35-39.
82. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Hamidov, E. (2023). YADRO ENERGIYASINING XOSSA VA XUSUSIYATLARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 182-186.
83. IN THE EDUCATIONAL FIELD OF PHYSICS LEVEL AND POSITION
84. SZ Jurakulov, O Nurboyev - GOLDEN BRAIN, 2023